

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation. The Concept of modernization of the Republic of Uzbekistan and general education sets an important task: to prepare the younger generation for life in a rapidly changing information society, in a world in which the process of the emergence of new knowledge is accelerating, the need for new professions and continuous training constantly arises.

Key words: Russian language, secondary school, Russian literature, higher school, Internet, information technology.

Currently, there is an increasing increase in the influence of media technologies on people. This has a particularly strong effect on a child, who would rather watch TV than read a book. A powerful flow of new information, advertising, the use of computer technology on television, the spread of game consoles, electronic toys and computers have a great influence on the upbringing of a child and his perception of the world around him. The nature of his favorite practical activity - games - also changes significantly, and his favorite heroes and hobbies also change. Previously, a child could receive information on any topic through different channels: textbook, reference literature, teacher's lecture, lesson notes. But today, taking into account modern realities, the teacher must introduce new methods of presenting information into the educational process. The question arises why this is necessary. A child's brain, tuned to receiving knowledge in the form of entertainment programs on television, will much more easily perceive the information offered in the lesson with the help of media. [3, 271]

It is necessary to teach every child to master, transform and use huge amounts of information in practical activities in a short period of time. It is very important to organize the learning process so that the child actively, with interest and enthusiasm works in class, sees the fruits of his labor and can appreciate them.

A combination of traditional teaching methods and modern information technologies, including computers, can help the teacher in solving this difficult problem. After all, using a computer in the classroom allows you to make the learning process mobile, strictly differentiated and individual.

Combining the capabilities of a TV, VCR, book, calculator, being a universal toy that can imitate other toys and a wide variety of games, a modern computer is at the same time an equal partner for a child, capable of responding very subtly to his actions and requests, which he sometimes needs lacks. On the other hand, this teaching method is very attractive for teachers: it helps them better assess the child's abilities and knowledge, understand him, and encourages them to look for new, non-traditional forms and methods of teaching [2, 90].

In practice, educational information technologies refer to all technologies that use special technical information tools (computers, audio, video, fragments from films). [1, 147]

When computers became widely used in education, the term "new information technology" was coined. Any pedagogical technology is information technology, since the basis of the technological learning process is information and its transformation. A better term for computer-assisted learning technologies is computer technology.

Computer (new information) learning technologies are the process of preparing and transmitting information to the learner, the means of which is a computer, laptop, tablet. [3, 97]

The computer gives the teacher new opportunities, allowing him and the student to enjoy the fascinating process of learning, not only pushing the walls of the school classroom with the power of imagination, but with the help of the latest technologies allows you to immerse yourself in a bright, colorful world. This activity causes an emotional uplift in children; even lagging students are willing to work with the computer. Increasing motivation and cognitive activity due to the variety of forms of work, the possibility of including a game moment: if you solve the examples correctly, open the picture, insert all the letters correctly - you will move closer to the goal of the fairy-tale hero [4, 67].

The introduction of information technologies in secondary education of the Republic of Uzbekistan plays a key role in modernizing the educational process and training qualified specialists for the digital economy. This process helps to improve the accessibility of education, improve its quality and develop the competencies necessary for successful adaptation to the requirements of the modern world. However, to achieve the full effectiveness of the implementation of information technology in the educational system, it is necessary to continue to develop the infrastructure, train teaching staff and ensure the availability of educational resources for all students. Only in this way will Uzbekistan be able to secure competitive personnel and sustainable development in the digital era.

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